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CHARACTERISTICS OF CLINICAL AND PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL COURSE OF CARDIOEMBOLIC STROKE

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ANNOTATION

Cerebrovascular diseases (CVD) have remained an urgent medical and social problem of modern society over the past decades. One of the main pathogenetic subtype of ischemic stroke is cardioembolic stroke (CES), which accounts for 22-39% of all stroke subtypes. CES is characterized by the rapid development of neurological symptoms (80% of cases) with its maximum severity in the first 5 minutes (47-74%) and large and medium-sized ischemic infarcts, which in 85% of cases are located in the carotid artery system, more often in the left middle cerebral artery (MCA).

The aim of the study: In this study, pathomorphological and clinical features of cardioembolic stroke, such as neurological signs, cerebral and myocardial infarcts in each sectional case, macroscopic and microscopic examinations were conducted and analyzed.

Materials and methods: This study is based on the analysis of the results of a comprehensive clinical and pathomorphological examination. The patients were selected for 1 year. Clinical observations were carried out at the first clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy in the Department of Intensive Neurology. The selection criteria were: 1) patients with ischemic stroke (IS) in combination with acute myocardial infarction and atrial fibrillation (main group); 2) persons with ischemic stroke (IS) without cardiac etiology (control group). Exclusion criteria: oncological and hematological diseases, severe renal and hepatic insufficiency. The analysis of 138 sectional cases with ischemic stroke and myocardial infarctions with atherosclerosis of cerebral and coronary arteries were carried out. Autopsies of all deceased patients were performed in the laboratory of the Republican Center of Pathological Anatomy. Macroscopic examination of the brain in all 138 cases determined the type, magnitude, localization, degree of organization of each cerebral infarction and the number of cerebral infarctions in each sectional case. In each case, microscopic examination of the brain and cerebral arteries with atherosclerotic changes were also performed. For microscopic examination, preparations were cut from the area of cerebral infarction, as well as from the borderline zone with infarction. Areas of the brain were poured into paraffin wax, preparations with 5-7 microns thick were prepared into the blocks, which were stained with hematoxylin and eosin, cresyl violet according to the modified Nissl method, according to the methods of Wangizov, Weigert, as well as laxol blue durable.

Results: Patients with IS and cardiac pathology – 120 people (group I) – 65 men and 55 women aged 48 to 77 years (62.6±5.8 years).

Patients with IS without cardiac pathology – 160 people (group II). Of these, 83 men and 77 women aged 56 to 81 years (68.4±5.4 years). Among the deceased were 93 men and 45 women aged 45 to 93 years (average age 69 ± 11 years). The average age of men was 60 years, of women - 69 years. In 113 cases (82%), an autopsy revealed a combination of atherosclerosis with arterial hypertension, in 9 (6.5%) - atherosclerosis with diabetes mellitus. The cause of death in 64 patients (47%) was pronounced edema of the brain with dislocation and insertion of brain stem and parts of the cerebellum into the large occipital foramen due to infarction of the brain. All cases are divided into 3 groups: Group 1 includes cases with infarcts localized in the carotid system (68 cases), group 2 - cases with infarcts localized in the vertebrobasilar system (36 cases), group 3 - cases with infarcts localized in the arteries of both systems (34 cases).

Conclusion: Brain infarctions in AS are characterized by great diversity regarding their localization; degree of organization, quantity; type; as well as: the main factors of their occurrence. The most numerous were medium infarcts and small deep infarcts, extensive, large infarcts and small superficial infarcts were less common. In our study, multiple atherosclerotic plaques, narrowing the lumen of the arteries by 30-80%, were found in 46% of cases. Moreover, in 28% of cases, plaques were located in different parts of the ICA - in the cerebral arteries of the MCA.

Keywords: cardioembolic stroke, ischemic infarcts, carotid system, vertebral basilar system, myocardial infarction, atrial fibrillation, autopsy.

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ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА КЛИНИКО-ПАТОМОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ТЕЧЕНИЯ КАРДИОЭМБОЛИЧЕСКОГО ИНСУЛЬТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цереброваскулярные заболевания (ССЗ) на протяжении последних десятилетий остаются актуальной медико-социальной проблемой современного общества. Одним из основных патогенетических подтипов ишемического инсульта является кардиоэмболический инсульт (КЭИ), на долю которого приходится 22-39% всех подтипов инсульта. Для КЭС характерно быстрое развитие неврологической симптоматики (80% случаев) с максимальной выраженностью в первые 5 минут (47-74%) и крупные и средние ишемические инфаркты, которые в 85% случаев локализуются в системе сонных артерий, чаще в левой средней мозговой артерии (СМА).

Цель исследования: В данном исследовании были проведены и проанализированы патоморфологические и клинические особенности кардиоэмболического инсульта, такие как неврологические признаки, инфаркты головного мозга и миокарда в каждом секционном случае, макроскопические и микроскопические исследования.

Материалы и методы: Исследование основано на анализе результатов комплексного клинико-патоморфологического обследования. Пациенты были отобраны сроком на 1 год. Клинические наблюдения проводились в первой клинике Ташкентской медицинской академии на кафедре интенсивной неврологии. Критериями отбора были: 1) пациенты с ишемическим инсультом (ИИ) в сочетании с острым инфарктом миокарда и мерцательной аритмией (основная группа); 2) лица с ишемическим инсультом (ИИ) некардиальной этиологии (контрольная группа). Проведен анализ 138 секционных случаев ишемического инсульта и инфаркта миокарда с атеросклерозом мозговых и коронарных артерий. Вскрытия всех умерших пациентов были проведены в лаборатории Республиканского центра патологической анатомии. Макроскопическое исследование головного мозга во всех 138 случаях определило вид, величину, локализацию, степень организации каждого инфаркта головного мозга и количество инфарктов головного мозга в каждом секционном случае. В каждом случае также проводилось микроскопическое исследование головного мозга и церебральных артерий с атеросклеротическими изменениями. Для микроскопического исследования препараты вырезали из зоны инфаркта мозга, а также из пограничной с инфарктом зоны.

Результаты: Пациенты с ИИ и патологией сердца – 120 человек (I группа) – 65 мужчин и 55 женщин в возрасте от 48 до 77 лет (62,6±5,8 года).

Больные ИИ без сердечной патологии – 160 человек (II группа). Из них 83 мужчины и 77 женщин в возрасте от 56 до 81 года (68,4±5,4 года). Среди умерших было 93 мужчины и 45 женщин в возрасте от 45 до 93 лет (средний возраст 69±11 лет). Средний возраст мужчин составил 60 лет, женщин - 69 лет. В 113 случаях (82%) на аутопсии выявлено сочетание атеросклероза с артериальной гипертензией, в 9 (6,5%) - атеросклероза с сахарным диабетом. Причиной смерти 64 больных (47%) стал выраженный отек головного мозга с дислокацией и встраиванием ствола мозга и частей мозжечка в большое затылочное отверстие вследствие инфаркта головного мозга. Все случаи разделены на 3 группы: в 1-ю группу вошли случаи с инфарктами, локализованными в системы сонной артерии (68 случаев), во 2-ю группу - случаи с инфарктами, локализованными в вертебробазиллярной системе (36 случаев), в 3-ю группу - случаи с локализацией инфарктов в артериях обеих систем (34 случая).

Заключение. Инфаркты головного мозга при АС характеризуются большим разнообразием локализации; степень организации, количество; тип; а также: основные факторы их возникновения. Наиболее многочисленными были средние инфаркты и малые глубокие инфаркты, реже встречались обширные, крупные инфаркты и малые поверхностные инфаркты. В нашем исследовании множественные атеросклеротические бляшки, сужающие просвет артерий на 30-80%, обнаружены в 46% случаев. При этом в 28% случаев бляшки располагались в разных отделах ВСА – в мозговых артериях СМА.

Ключевые слова: кардиоэмболический инсульт, ишемические инфаркты, каротидная система, вертебробазиллярная система, инфаркт миокарда, мерцательная аритмия, аутопсия.

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ANNOTATSIYA

So'nggi o'n yilliklarda serebrovaskulyar kasalliklar (CVD) zamonaviy jamiyatning dolzarb tibbiy va ijtimoiy muammosi bo'lib qolmoqda. Ishemik insultning asosiy patogenetik kichik turlaridan biri kardioembolik insult (KEI) bo'lib, u barcha insult kichik turlarining 22-39% ni tashkil qiladi. KEI nevrologik simptomlarning tez rivojlanishi (80% hollarda) dastlabki 5 daqiqada maksimal zararlanish (47-74%) va katta va o'rta ishemik infarktlar bilan tavsiflanadi, bu 85% hollarda uyqu arteriyalari sistemasida joylashib, arteriya havzasi ko'pincha chap o'rta miya arteriyasidadir (O'MA).

Tadqiqot maqsadi: Ushbu tadqiqotda kardioembolik insultning patomorfologik va klinik xususiyatlari, masalan, nevrologik belgilar, har bir seksion holatdagi miya va miokard infarktlarining makroskopik va mikroskopik tadqiqotlari o'tkazildi va tahlil qilindi.

Tadqiqot materiali va usullar: Tadqiqot keng qamrovli klinik va patomorfologik tekshiruv natijalarini tahlil qilishga asoslangan. Bemorlar 1 yil muddat davomida saralab olindi. Klinik kuzatuvlar Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi birinchi klinikasida intensiv nevrologiya kafedrasida o'tkazildi. Tanlash mezonlari: 1) o'tkir miokard infarkti va bo'lmachalar fibrilatsiyasi (asosiy guruh) fonida ishemik insult (II) o'tkazgan bemorlar; 2) yurak patologiyasi bo'lmagan ishemik insult (II) kuzatilgan shaxslar (nazorat guruhi). Miya va koronar arteriyalarning aterosklerozi bilan ishemik insult va miokard infarkti kuzatilgan 138 ta seksiyasi tahlili o'tkazildi. Vafot etgan barcha bemorlarning jasadlari Respublika patologik anatomiya markazi laboratoriyasida tahlildan o'tkazildi. Barcha 138 holatda miyaning makroskopik tekshiruv har bir miya infarkti turini, hajmini, joylashishini, tashkil etilganlik darajasini va har bir qismli holatda miya infarkti soni aniqlandi. Har bir holatda, aterosklerotik o'zgarishlar bilan miya va miya tomirlarining mikroskopik tekshiruv ham amalga oshirildi. Mikroskopik tekshirish uchun miya infarkti hududidan, shuningdek, infarkt bilan chegaradosh hududdan namunalari olindi.

Natijalar: II va yurak patologiyasi bo'lgan bemorlar - 120 kishi (I guruh) - 48 yoshdan 77 yoshgacha bo'lgan 65 erkak va 55 ayol (62,6±5,8 yosh).

Yurak patologiyasi bo'lmagan II bilan og'rikan bemorlar - 160 kishi (II guruh). Ulardan 56 yoshdan 81 yoshgacha (68,4±5,4 yosh) 83 nafari erkaklar va 77 nafari ayollardir. Halok bo'lganlar orasida 45 yoshdan 93 yoshgacha bo'lgan (o'rtacha yoshi 69±11 yosh) 93 nafar erkak va 45 nafar ayol bor. Erkaklar o'rtacha yoshi 60 yosh, ayollar 69 yosh. 113 holatda (82%) otopsiyada aterosklerozning arterial gipertenziya bilan kombinatsiyasi, 9 tasida (6,5%) qandli diabet bilan ateroskleroz aniqlangan. 64 bemorda (47%) o'lim sababi miya infarkti tufayli miya ustuni va miyacha qismlarining foramen magnumga dislokatsiyasi va integratsiyalashuvi bilan og'ir miya shishi bo'lgan. Barcha holatlar 3 guruhga bo'lingan: 1-guruhga uyqu arteriya tizimida lokalizatsiya qilingan infarktlar (68 ta holat), 2-guruhga vertebrobazilar tizimida lokalizatsiya qilingan infarktlar (36 ta holat), 3-guruhga - ikkala tizimning arteriyalarida infarktlarning lokalizatsiyasi bo'lgan holatlar (34 ta holat) infarktlar kiritilgan.

Xulosa. Aterosklerozdagi miya infarktlari turli xil lokalizatsiya bilan tavsiflanadi; tashkil etish darajasi, miqdori; turi; va shuningdek: ularning paydo bo'lishining asosiy omillari. Eng ko'p o'rta infarktlar va kichik chuqur infarktlar aniqlangan bo'lsa, katta infarktlar va kichik yuzaki infarktlar kamroq tarqalgan; Bizning tadqiqotimizda arteriyalarning ichki qatlamini 30-80% ga toraytiruvchi ko'plab aterosklerotik pilaklar 46% hollarda topilgan. Bundan tashqari, 28% hollarda pilakcha IUA ning turli qismlarida – O'UANing miya arteriyalarida joylashgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kardioembolik insult, ishemik infarkt, uyqu arteriyasi tizimi, vertebrobazilar tizim, miokard infarkti, bo'lmachalar fibrilatsiyasi, autopsiya.

Introduction. Cerebrovascular diseases (CVD) have remained an urgent medical and social problem of modern society over the past decades. High morbidity, mortality and disability, as well as great economic damage associated with vascular diseases of the brain, necessitate further improvement of medical care for them [1, 2]. One of the main pathogenetic subtype of ischemic stroke is cardioembolic stroke (CES), which accounts for 22-39% of all stroke subtypes. CES is characterized by the rapid development of neurological symptoms (80% of cases) with its maximum severity in the first 5 minutes (47-74%) and large and medium-sized ischemic infarcts, which in 85% of cases are located in the carotid artery system, more often in the left middle cerebral artery (MCA) [67, 103, 104]. In connection with the above, pathomorphological studies are very relevant, allowing us to verify clinical data on diagnostic signs and predictors of the cardioembolic subtype of stroke. According to the BASIC classification (Boston Acute Stroke Imaging Scale) [181], only large and small infarcts are distinguished. A large infarction is diagnosed with occlusion of the intracranial part of the internal carotid artery (ICA), the horizontal part of the middle cerebral artery (MCA) or the basilar artery (BA). According to sectional data, such infarcts mainly occur as a result of obstructive atherothrombosis of ICA, VA or BA, less often — cardiogenic or arterio-arterial thromboembolism [9, 11, 15].

A.N.Evdokimenko, T.S.Gulevskaya (2008) published the results of autopsy analysis of 146 cases of cerebral infarction: 30% of patients have thromboembolism from the heart caused extensive, large and medium-sized infarctions in the ICA system, while myocardial infarction (MI) was detected in 14% of cases [28].

The main part. This study is based on the analysis of the results of a comprehensive clinical and pathomorphological examination. The patients were selected for 6 years. Clinical observations were carried out at the first clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy in the Department of Intensive Neurology. The selection criteria were: 1) patients with ischemic stroke (IS) in combination with acute myocardial infarction and atrial fibrillation (main group); 2) persons with ischemic stroke (IS) without cardiac etiology (control group). Exclusion criteria: oncological and hematological diseases, severe renal and hepatic insufficiency.

Since in our study, 120 patients among the studied patients had atrial fibrillation/myocardial infarction in a comorbid background, we divided all patients into 2 groups based on the presence of cardiac pathology.

Patients with IS and cardiac pathology – 120 people (group I) – 65 men and 55 women aged 48 to 77 years (62.6±5.8 years).

Patients with IS without cardiac pathology – 160 people (group II). Of these, 83 men and 77 women aged 56 to 81 years (68.4±5.4 years).

Table 1.

Distribution of patients into groups by gender and age

Groups	Group I		Group II		Total	
Number of patients	120 (42,9%)		160 (57,1%)		280 (100%)	
Average age (M±σ)	62,6±5,8		68,4±5,4		64,5±6,2	
Sex	m	F	m	F	M	F
Number of patients	65 (54,2%)	55 (45,8%)	83 (51,9%)	77 (48,1%)	148 (52,9%)	132 (47,1%)
Average age (M±σ)	57,9±4,7	61,1±4,1	61,2±3,7	63,6±3,9	59,6±5,6	62,8±7,1

The analysis of 138 sectional cases with ischemic stroke and myocardial infarctions with atherosclerosis of cerebral and coronary arteries was carried out. Autopsies of all deceased patients were performed in the laboratory of the Republican Center of Pathological

Anatomy. Among the deceased were 93 men and 45 women aged 45 to 93 years (average age 69 ± 11 years). The average age of men was 60 years, of women – 69 years. The distribution of deceased patients by age group and gender is shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Distribution of deceased patients by age group and gender

Sex	Age groups, years				
	45-49	50-59	60-69	70-79	81-84
Male	16	25	34	18	-
Female	2	7	15	14	7
Total	18	32	49	32	7

In 113 cases (82%), an autopsy revealed a combination of atherosclerosis with arterial hypertension, in 9 (6.5%) - atherosclerosis with diabetes mellitus. The cause of death in 64 patients (47%) was pronounced edema of the brain with dislocation and insertion of brain stem and sections of the cerebellum into the large occipital foramen due to infarction of the brain. The death of 36 patients (26%) was due to

massive thromboembolism of the pulmonary trunk and pulmonary arteries from deep veins of the lower extremities, 22 (17%) — acute cardiovascular insufficiency associated with myocardial infarction (13 cases) or acute diffuse ischemic changes in cardiomyocytes in combination with small-focal and large-focal cardiosclerosis of the left ventricle (9 cases), 15 - other types of visceral pathology (Table 4).

Table 3.

Causes of death of patients (n=138)

The cause of death of patients	Number of deaths
Edema of the brain with dislocation of brain stem	64
Massive thromboembolism of the pulmonary trunk or pulmonary arteries	36
Acute heart failure	22
Acute respiratory failure	6

Acute cardiopulmonary insufficiency	4
Acute renal failure	4
Hemorrhagic shock	1
hemotamponade of the pericardium	1

Macroscopic examination of the brain in all 138 cases determined the type, magnitude, localization, degree of organization of each cerebral infarction and the number of cerebral infarctions in each sectional case. In each case, microscopic examination of the brain and cerebral arteries with atherosclerotic changes was also performed. For microscopic examination, sections were cut from the area of cerebral infarction, as well as from the borderline zone with infarction. Areas of the brain were poured into paraffin wax, sections 5-7 microns thick were prepared from the blocks, which were stained with hematoxylin and eosin, cresyl violet according to the modified Nissl method, according to the methods of Wangizon, Weigert, as well as laxol blue durable. Sections of the cerebral arteries with atherosclerotic changes were poured into paraffin, sections 5-7 microns thick were prepared from the blocks, which were stained with hematoxylin and eosin. All cases are divided into 3 groups: Group 1 includes cases with infarcts localized in the carotid system (68 cases), group 2 - cases with infarcts localized in the vertebrobasilar system (36 cases), group 3 - cases with infarcts localized in the arteries of both systems (34 cases). In each group, atherosclerotic changes in cerebral vessels were studied, the frequency of detection of tandem atherostenosis in the carotid system and artery of vertebral-basilar system, myocardial infarction and large-focal cardiosclerosis was determined. A comparative analysis of atherosclerotic changes in the arteries of the brain, changes in the heart

caused by atherosclerosis of the coronary arteries, the frequency of detection of tandem atherostenosis, as well as the magnitude, localization, number and causes of cerebral infarctions was carried out between the three groups. In 68 cases (out of 138), cerebral infarctions were localized in the arteries of the carotid system. In the study of the brain, atherosclerotic plaques in the carotid system were detected in 67 cases, in the vertebral - basilar artery system in 59 cases, and with approximately the same frequency on the right and left. The most pronounced changes were found in the sinus region of the ICA and in the MCA ($p < 0.04$). Atherosclerotic plaques in these arteries were detected in 54 and 56 cases, atherostenosis $> 50\%$ - in 18 and 14 cases, respectively. In the plaques located in the CS calcification and hemorrhage were often detected (18 out of 54 cases). On the contrary, in MCA, all plaques had fibrosis. Atherosclerotic plaques in the remaining examined arteries of the brain were detected less frequently (18-46 cases). At the same time, plaques were found in the cerebral part of the internal carotid artery, the intracranial part of the vertebral artery and the posterior cerebral artery in 32-46 cases, including hemodynamically significant atherostenosis ($> 50\%$) in 7-13 cases. The plaques were mainly fibrous, in isolated cases, foci of atheromatosis and calcifications were detected in the plaques. Atherosclerotic changes in the carotid artery, ICA siphon, ACA and VA were observed least often (Table 4).

Table 4.

Localization and severity of atherosclerotic changes in cerebral arteries in cases with infarcts

Localization of plaques	Total number of cases	Degree of atherostenosis (number of cases)				The nature of the lesion of the vessel (number of cases)		Athero-thrombosis
		$< 20\%$	$> 20\%$, $< 50\%$	$> 50\%$, $< 70\%$	$> 70\%$	Fibrous plaques	Complicated atherostenosis	
Arteries of the carotid system								
ACC	18	14	3	1	-	18	-	2
Syphon of CA	54*	23	13	6	12	35	18	17
Syphon of ICA	27	21	3	1	2	18	9	4
The brain part of ICA	40	27	6	4	3	37	3	3
ACA	23	16	1	3	3	23	-	-
MCA	56*	35	7	7	7	56	-	5
Arteries of the vertebral-basilar system								
Ostium of VA	21	7	6	4	4	21	-	-
The brain part of VA	37	21	3	7	6	35	2	-
BA	46	35	4	5	2	45	1	-
PCA	32	23	-	6	3	32	-	-

* - significant difference, $p < 0,05$.

During morphological examination of the heart, there were no changes in it only 2 of the deceased cases, in 26 only small-focal cardiosclerosis or left ventricular myocardial hypertrophy was

determined. Large-focal cardiosclerosis was detected in half of the cases, while the scar was more often located in the anterior or posterior walls of the left ventricle (19 cases). In 10 cases, left ventricular

myocardial infarction was detected, in half of which it was combined with large-focal cardiosclerosis. Parietal thrombi in the cavity of the left ventricle were detected in 4 cases. In the study of the brain, 1 infarction was detected in 37 of the 68 studied cases, in 31 cases — from 2 to 7

infarcts, mainly 2-4 cerebral infarcts (see Table.3.2.). In total, 138 brain infarctions were detected in this group, among which 17 were extensive, 19 were large, 67 were medium, 18 were small deep infarcts and 17 were small superficial infarcts.

Table 5.

The number of infarcts in 1 sectional case

	The number of infarcts in 1 sectional case							Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Number of cases	37	13	9	6	-	2	1	68

The cause of all extensive infarctions (17) was obliteration of the lumen of the ICA, while, as indicated in Table 7, in 9 cases, AT of the ICA was detected, most often in the area of its sinus, less often in the siphon or cerebral part. In 6 cases, the occurrence of extensive infarctions was caused by the ICA or its branches, in 2 - AE of the

cerebral part of the ICA by a fragment of a parietal thrombus from the aortic arch or CS. Extensive infarcts were mainly single (11 out of 17 cases). Less often (6 cases) they were combined with smaller infarcts. At the same time, in 1 case, extensive and large infarctions were detected in both hemispheres of the brain due to AT of both ICA.

Table 6.

The causes of cerebral infarctions of various sizes and localization in the arteries of the carotid system

Localization and size infarcts of the brain	Cause of infarcts of the brain				Total
	TA	AT	CE	AE	
ICA (extensive)	-	9	6	2	17
MCA (large)	-	11	4	4	19
Cortical branches of MCA	4	10	15	6	35
Medium	3	11	15	6	35
Small superficial infarcts	1	-	-	-	1
Deep branches of MCA	8	4	3	4	19
Medium	1	2	3	5	11
Small deep infarcts	8	1	-	-	9
Cortical branches of ACA	5	2	1	-	8
Medium	1	2	1	-	4
Small superficial infarcts	4	-	-	-	4
Deep branches of ACA	6	4	1	1	12
Medium	-	1	1	1	3
Small deep infarcts	7	2	-	-	9
Approximal blood supply area of ACA	11	7	6	1	25
MCA and PCA					
Medium	3	2	5	1	11
Small superficial infarcts	8	5	-	-	13
Total	37	45	37	19	138

The death of patients with such infarcts occurred early from the onset of stroke (after a few days), the cause of death in most cases was edema of the brain. The average infarcts were predominantly white, and a hemorrhagic component was detected in 10 out of 62 infarcts. The vast

majority of medium-sized infarcts had signs of organization gliomesodermal scar (56 out of 62). At the same time, lipophages, newly formed vessels and hypertrophied astrocytes were detected in infarcts.

In 36 cases (out of 138), infarctions were localized in the vertebrobasilar artery system (VBS). In the study of brain, atherosclerotic plaques in AVBS were detected in 35 cases, in ACS — in 34 cases. The most pronounced changes were found in the intracranial part of the VA and in the BA ($p < 0.05$). Atherosclerotic plaques in these arteries were detected in 30 and 33 cases, respectively, and hemodynamically significant atherostenosis ($>50\%$) - in 15 and 18

cases. The identified plaques were mainly fibrous, hemorrhage and calcifications (Table 6).

In the study of brain, in the vast majority of cases (28 out of 36), multiple cerebral infarctions were detected (from 2 to 15 cerebral infarctions in 1 sectional case, $p < 0.03$), mainly from 2 to 6 (Table 7). In 8 cases, 1 extensive, large or medium infarction was detected in the brain stem, hemisphere cerebellum or occipital lobes of the brain (3 and 2 cases, respectively).

Table 7.

The number of infarcts in 1 sectional case of 2nd group

	The number of infarcts in 1 sectional case											Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	11	15	
The number of cases	8	8	2	4	5	3	1	2	1	1	1	36

The predominant localization of infarcts was the brain stem, in which 73 infarcts (out of 147) were located. At the same time, infarcts were mainly found in the medulla oblongata of the brain (49 infarcts), mainly in its basilar part (30 infarcts). 7 extensive infarcts involved the entire brain stem or several parts of it. Infarctions were detected 2 times

less frequently in the cerebellum (35 infarcts) and in the PCA system (35 infarcts). In the cerebellum, 1 large infarction captured the entire hemisphere of the cerebellum, 8 were localized in deep parts of the hemisphere (mainly in the area of the dentate nuclei in the area of adjacent blood supply to the cerebellar arteries).

Table 8.

Causes of cerebral infarctions of various sizes and localization in the arteries of the vertebral-basilar system

Localization and sizes of infarcts of the brain	Cause of infarcts			Total
	TA	AT	CA	
Brain stem	33	40	-	73
Extensive	-	7	-	7
Large	-	3	-	3
Medium	1	6	-	7
Small deep infarcts	32	24	-	56
Hemisphere of cerebellum	21	14	-	35
Large	-	1	-	1
Medium	7	8	-	15
Small superficial infarcts	9	2	-	11
Small deep infarcts	5	3	-	8
Posterior cerebral artery	25	8	2	35
Large	-	1	-	1
Medium	7	4	2	13
Small superficial infarcts	11	1	-	12
Small deep infarcts	7	2	-	9
The area of adjacent blood supply to the cerebral arteries	3	1	-	4

Medium	1	-	-	1
Small superficial infarcts	2	1	-	3
Total	82	63	2	147

Thus, in 36 out of 138 cases, infarcts were localized in the vertebrobasilar artery system. In these cases, AS was most pronounced in the intracranial part of the VA and in the BA. Tandem atherostenosis of AVBS was detected in 22 cases. In 23 cases, obstructive atherothrombosis of AVBS was observed: intracranial VA or BA (18 cases), MCA or posterior inferior cerebellar artery (5). In 16 cases (44%), signs of coronary artery disease were revealed: large-focal cardiosclerosis (13 cases), left ventricular myocardial infarction (2) or a combination of them (1). In cases of autopsy, chronic ischemic disease

was revealed - large-focal postinfarction cardiosclerosis, atherosclerotic small-focal diffuse cardiosclerosis. Anatomical focal postinfarction cardiosclerosis is presented in the form of scar tissue, whitish in color, with irregular contours, and was more often detected on the posterior wall of the left ventricle. Histologically, a fibrous field surrounded by hypertrophied cardiomyocytes was detected. In atrial fibrillation, morphological changes were expressed in focal sclerosis, mainly around blood vessels, focal necrosis of single cardiomyocytes, dystrophy - simple myocardial obesity.

Figure 4.6. On a planar section of the wall of the left ventricle, there is an extensive whitish scar with indistinct contours (macropreparation).

Fig. 4.7. Extensive fibrous field, preserved hypertrophied muscle fibers in a cross section around. Stained with hematoxylin and eosin. The magnification is 10x10.

When comparing the degree of atherostenosis of the cerebral arteries in groups 1 and 2, it was found that the degree of atherostenosis of the ICA and its branches was approximately the same in cases with infarcts localized in the AX and AVBS basins, while the number of

plaques in VA, BA and PCA, as well as the degree of atherostenosis of these arteries were significantly higher ($p < 0.03$) in cases with infarcts localized in the AVBS, compared with cases in which infarcts were localized in the ACS only.

Table 9.

Localization and severity of atherosclerotic changes in cerebral arteries in cases with infarcts 2nd group

Localization of plaques	The total number of cases	Degree of atherostenosis (number of cases)				Character of arteries (number of cases)		Athero-trombosis
		<20%	<50%	>50%, <70%	>70%	Fibrous plaques	Complicated atherostenosis	
Carotid system arteries								
ACC	12	11	1			12		
CA	22	11	4	3	4	13	9	
Siphon of ICA	12	10	1	1		6	6	
Brain part of ICA	23	14	1	7	1	22	1	
ACA	14	9	1	4		14		
MCA	31	16	4	10	1	31		
Vertebra-basilar system arteries								
Ostium of VA	12	2		3	7	11	1	
Intracranial part of VA	30*	12	3	5	10	27	"y	13
BA	33*	12	3	11	7	30	3	8
PCA	30	16	2	6	6	30		1

In most cases (22 out of 36), multiple plaques stenosing by 40-80% were detected in the AVBS, usually located in the intracranial part of the PA, BA and PCA (16 cases), less often in the mouth of the VA (6 cases). At the same time, the detection rate of tandem atherostenosis of the arteries of this system was significantly higher than in group 1 ($p < 0.0001$).

During the reporting period, we included 280 patients (148 (52.9%) men and 132 (47.1%) women) with neuroimaging MRI-verified signs of acute ischemic changes that did not end in death in the acute period of AI. All patients with stroke were admitted to the clinic in the acute period of the disease. Impaired consciousness of varying severity was observed in 36 patients (12.9%). There were 14 patients in a comatose state at admission, which was 5% of the total number of patients. In somnolence, which was expressed by lethargy, drowsiness, disorientation, there were 12 patients (4.34%). Headache bothered 193 patients (68.9%), in 58 it was diffuse, in 84 it was localized in the frontal-parietal region, in 13 in the occipital region of the head, in 47 it was unilateral, in 9 patients they could not determine its exact localization. The nature of the headache was compressive, bursting, constant. Dizziness was observed in 173 patients (61.8%), more often of a non-systemic nature, nausea and vomiting in 71 (25.4%) and 40 (14.30%) patients, respectively. Examination of cranial nerves revealed homonymous hemianopsia in 38 patients. Pathology of the oculomotor nerves in the form of gaze paresis and installation nystagmus was most often observed in 27 patients (9.6%). Pupillary reflexes to light (direct and indirectly) were weakened and absent in 24 (8.5%), respectively. The soreness of the Valle points was noted mainly on the side of the lesion and was observed in 172 patients (61.4%). Central paresis of the VII cranial nerve – in the form of smoothness of the nasolabial fold and the inability to perform lower facial tests was observed in almost all patients, but in varying degrees of severity. Central paresis of the facial nerve with complicity of the upper branch is noted in 67 patients (23.8%). Dysarthric speech was observed in 22 patients (7.9%). Central paresis of the XII pair was detected in 213 patients (76.1%), which was

expressed in a deviation of the tongue in the opposite direction from the focus without the phenomenon of atrophy and fibrillation. In the motor sphere, all patients had paresis and paralysis. In 71 (25.4%) patients, paresis was accompanied by an early increase in muscle tone according to the spastic type and in 160 (57%) patients with an initial decrease in muscle tone. Monoparesis was observed in 20 patients (7%), in 76 (27.1%) - mild hemiparesis, in 62 (22.2%) - moderate and in 49 (17.5%) - severe. Hemiplegia was observed in 24 (8.6%) patients. The study of tendon reflexes revealed their decrease on the lesion side in 58 patients (21%), the absence of -7 (2.5%), an increase in 167 (59.6%). Pathological reflexes were characteristic of the majority of the examined patients: Babinsky's symptom was observed in 211 (75.4%), Oppenheim's symptom in 29 (10.3%) patients. Foot and knee clonus were observed in 11 (3.97%) patients. In 102 (36.5%) patients, it was not possible to reliably verify disorders in the sensitive area due to impaired consciousness and complete adequacy of patients due to aphasia. Sensitive disorders in the remaining 129 (46%) patients were characterized by hemisyndromicity from deep hemianesthesia of all types of sensitivity to mild disorders. In the study of coordination of movements, 73 (26.2%) of the examined patients could not perform coordination tests on paralyzed limbs due to deep paresis, 138 (49.2%) patients performed paretic finger-nasal and knee-heel tests. The test for adiadochokinesis, dysmetry and the symptom of a backshock was positive in 16 (5.6%), 7 (2.4%) and 2 (0.71%) patients, respectively. Meningeal symptoms were observed in 9 (3.17%) patients, all of them had stiffness of the occipital muscles, 4 (1.43%) had a symptom of Kernig on 2 sides. Cortical speech disorders were observed in 62 (22.2%) patients. Of these, 27 (9.64%) had motor aphasia, 11 (3.93%) had sensory aphasia, and 24 (8.578%) patients had sensorimotor aphasia. Summarizing the main neurological manifestations of ischemic stroke, we came to the conclusion that in patients the clinical picture of the lesion of the carotid system was characterized by a predominance of focal symptoms: central paresis of VII and XII pairs of cranial nerves, the presence of mono-, hemiparesis or hemiplegia, the appearance of

pathological reflexes combined with sensitive disorders in the form of superficial or total mono-hemianesthesia. To objectify the condition of patients with hemispheric ischemic strokes, their neurological status was assessed using two complementary scales - Scandinavian and

NIHSS. The average clinical score at admission in patients with hemispheric ischemic strokes was 14.5 ± 2.1 on the NIHSS scale and 24.1 ± 2.8 on the Scandinavian scale, which corresponds to the average severity of the disease.

Table 10.
Assessment of the neurological status in the dynamics of the disease in patients in the acute period according to clinical scales patients with ischemic stroke(n=280)

	1-day	3-day	10- day
NIHSS scale	14,5±2,1	12,9±1,8	9,1±1,6*
Scandinavian scale	24,1±2,8	27,5±3,1	34,2±3,2*

Note: *-significantly compared with the data for 1 day (*-P <0.05)

Conclusion.

Stroke is a clinical syndrome that is an acute disorder of cerebral circulation, characterized by the sudden (within minutes, hours) appearance of focal and/or cerebral neurological symptoms, which persist for more than 24 hours or lead to the death of the patient in a shorter period of time due to cerebrovascular pathology [Donnan G. Stroke / G. A. Donnan, M. Fisher, M. Macleod, S. MDavis // The Lancet. - 2008. - No. 371. - P. 1612-1623]. Brain infarctions in AS are characterized by great diversity regarding their localization; degree of organization, quantity; type; as well as: the main factors of their occurrence. The most numerous were medium infarcts and small deep infarcts, extensive, large infarcts and small superficial infarcts were less common. In 68 cases, infarctions were localized in the carotid system,

in 36 - only the vertebra-basilar system, in 34 - in the arterial basins of both systems. In most cases (67%), infarctions were multiple (from 2 to 15 in one case), in a third of cases they were single. But according to the literature, in approximately 40% of cases, ischemic cerebrovascular accidents are caused by atherosclerosis of the main arteries of the head [8, 9, 23, 87, 114], which was fully confirmed in our study, since atherosclerotic changes in the ICA and VA caused the occurrence of cerebral infarctions in 42 % of cases. In our study, multiple atherosclerotic plaques, narrowing the lumen of the arteries by 30-80%, were found in 46% of cases. Moreover, in 28% of cases, plaques were located in different parts of the ICA - in the cerebral arteries of the MCA.

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ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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